

ASSESSMENT OF THE PERFORMANCE OF TWO FORMULATIONS OF INTERFACE ELEMENTS FOR THE SIMULATION OF FATIGUE INDUCED DELAMINATION

U. Galvanetto^(1,2), P. Robinson⁽²⁾, A. Cerioni⁽³⁾, C. Lopez Armas⁽²⁾

⁽¹⁾Dipartimento di Costruzioni e Trasporti, Università degli Studi di Padova, Italy
galva@dic.unipd.it

⁽²⁾Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College London, UK
p.robinson@imperial.ac.uk

⁽³⁾Dipartimento di Ingegneria Meccanica, Università degli Studi di Cagliari, Italy
agcerioni@gmail.com

SUMMARY

Recently interface elements have been used in the simulation of fatigue induced crack propagation. This work presents a one degree of freedom mathematical model which can be used to assess systematically the performance of different interface element formulations in an efficient and rational way.

Keywords: interface elements, fatigue delamination, numerical modelling, composites.

INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix fibre reinforced composites are finding an ever increasing use in many fields of engineering. However their more extensive application is being inhibited by an incomplete understanding of their various failure modes. Delamination, i.e. the separation of originally adjacent layers, is one of the most common failure modes in laminated composites. It may be induced by in-service interlaminar stresses present, for example, at free edges and ply drops and during impact. The interlaminar stresses can be the result of quasi-static, dynamic or fatigue loading of the composite component. The present work only deals with the last case when the delamination propagates by a deterioration of the interface between laminae due to cyclic loading

In general laminated carbon fibre reinforced polymer matrix composites behave much better than metals under fatigue loading. Usually stiffness and strength of laminated composite structures under fatigue loading degrade in a much more gradual way than in metallic components but degradation due to fatigue propagation of delamination can be a significant problem for polymer matrix composites..

Modern computational techniques are routinely used in the design of complex structures and they have to be equipped with innovative tools to simulate new failure modes, such as delamination in composite materials. Interface elements have been for finite element (FE) codes to predict delamination due to quasi static and impact loads [1-3]. Their formulations, often based on the cohesive zone model [4, 5], have been recently extended to include the possibility of simulating fatigue driven delamination [6, 7]. Strategies for incorporating fatigue failure into interface elements are still being investigated. The comprehensive investigation of such strategies can require a very

large number (many thousands) of FE model runs to clearly establish the dependence on key parameters.

In the present paper a simple model is presented for a systematic and fast evaluation of the performance of constitutive laws implemented in interface elements for the simulation of fatigue-induced delamination growth. The simple, one dimensional, mathematical model isolates the interface elements from the interaction with other parts of a FE model since it does not involve any finite element mesh of the composite material; this enables a careful examination of three key aspects of modelling fatigue-driven delamination:

- interface constitutive laws;
- damage definitions;
- fatigue degradation strategies.

Even though the model is restricted to Mode I fatigue-driven delamination, the understanding gained about the above aspects will be equally applicable to Mode II and Mixed-mode delamination growth modelling strategies. Finally due to its simplicity, the mathematical model is very efficient from a computational point of view so that parametric studies involving hundreds of thousands of different sets of parameter values are possible in a relatively short time.

THE ONE-DIMENSIONAL MODEL

Consider the cylinder of radius R , shown in Figure 1, which, under static loading, rolls in a clockwise direction on a horizontal surface. The contact point of the initial configuration is indicated by the letter A, whereas C indicates the current contact point. The horizontal surface is composed of two zero-thickness layers. In the initial state the two layers are coincident. As the cylinder rotates the lower layer remains fixed and the upper layer adheres to the surface of the cylinder at the contact point, C, and remains adhered between A and C as the contact point advances (the layers are designated as 'upper' and 'lower' layer in Figure 1 for convenience). The upper layer is therefore separated from the lower layer in the zone behind the contact point. The separation of the two layers is opposed by a system of vertical springs, with uniform spacing Δl , which are initially unstressed but become stressed as the two layers separate. The only degree of freedom of the system is the rotation of the cylinder θ , which is the angle swept through by the line OA on the cylinder cross section, which was vertical in the initial configuration. The position of the current contact point, which represents the crack length, can be identified as:

$$x_{con} = \theta R \quad (1)$$

In the initial state the contact point is at $x=0$ (where x is measured from the left hand edge of the zero-thickness layers) and the rotation, θ , of the cylinder is zero. The position $x=0$ is also the position of the first spring.

A clockwise moment is applied to the cylinder to cause it to rotate and the upper layer is lifted and separated from the lower one, as shown in Figure 1. In this way the springs will be activated, will elongate and offer resistance to the change in rotation. The role of the springs in this simple model is that of interface elements in an FE model. The

mechanical behavior of the springs will therefore depend on their constitutive law which will be defined in such a way to enable the stress in the spring to eventually reduce to zero (representing interlaminar failure) as the layer separation increases. The length of R is to be chosen as very large compared to the elongation at which the stretched springs fail (δ_c) so that the springs can be considered to remain vertical while they are stressed.

Figure 1: the one degree of freedom model.

In the present work the stress in each spring is a function only of the displacement at the position of the spring, i.e. the springs act independently with no interaction between adjacent springs. This assumption corresponds to linear interface elements integrated with a Newton-Cotes rule [8]. Other integration rules or higher order elements could be easily implemented in the model.

Kinematics

Given the uniform spring spacing Δl , once the rotation θ is known simple calculations provide the number of elongated springs, n , their elongation, δ_i , and their distance from the contact point, d_i . Then, for a given constitutive law, it is possible to calculate the spring stress, $\sigma_i = f(\delta_i)$, the associated force (per unit length of the cylinder axis in the two-dimensional model), $F_i = \sigma_i \Delta l$, and moment with respect to the contact point, $M_i = F_i d_i$. The total moment (M_t) generated by the springs is found by summing all the moments M_i of all the elongated springs:

$$M_t = \sum_{i=1}^n M_i \quad (2)$$

This is the magnitude of the moment which must be applied to the cylinder to maintain it in equilibrium for a given applied rotation θ .

Damage-based constitutive laws

Interface spring constitutive laws can be expressed in terms of a damage variable. In Damage Mechanics [9, 10] damage indicates surface discontinuities in the form of micro-cracks, or volume discontinuities in the form of cavities in a considered volume element. A material is considered to be free of any damage if it does not have

cracks and cavities at the microscopic scale. The final damage state is reached when the considered volume element is completely fractured.

The theory of damage describes the evolution of the constitutive behaviour of the material between the undamaged state and macroscopic crack initiation. Damage cannot be measured directly and its quantitative evaluation is linked to the definition of the variables chosen to represent it. In the simplest formulation the damaged state of a material is characterised by the value of a scalar variable D which is a non decreasing quantity. Usually damage is defined so that for the undamaged state it is equal to zero and for the failure state it is equal to unity, therefore the following relationships apply

$$\left| \begin{array}{ll} D = 0 & \text{undamaged} \\ 0 < D < 1 & \text{damaged} \\ D = 1 & \text{failed} \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

The interface constitutive laws used in this work are expressed in terms of damage. Two components of damage are considered in the paper: static damage, D_s , and fatigue damage, D_f which is discussed later.

Figure 2: (a) bilinear and (b) third order polynomial constitutive laws.

The static damage, D_s , can be considered a measure of the degradation of the initial stiffness, K , as follows

$$\sigma = (1-D_s) K \delta \quad (4)$$

The bilinear constitutive law, shown in Figure 2a, can be defined by equation 4 with the following definition of the damage variable [11]:

$$D_s = \begin{cases} 0 & 0 \leq \delta \leq \delta_0 \\ \left(\frac{\delta - \delta_0}{\delta} \right) \left(\frac{\delta_c}{\delta_c - \delta_0} \right) & \delta_0 < \delta < \delta_c \\ 1 & \delta \geq \delta_c \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where δ is the elongation of the spring, δ_0 the maximum elongation in the linear elastic range and δ_c the value of the elongation at failure. In a similar way the third-order polynomial law, shown in Figure 2b, can also be expressed by equation 4 providing the damage variable, D_s , is defined as [11]:

$$D_s = \begin{cases} 2 \frac{\delta}{\delta_c} - \left(\frac{\delta}{\delta_c} \right)^2 & 0 \leq \delta \leq \delta_c \\ 1 & \delta > \delta_c \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Fatigue degradation strategy

In order to simplify the calculation process some assumptions are made [12]. The first one is related to the cyclic load which is assumed to be sinusoidal and oscillating between zero and a maximum value. It would be very computationally expensive to simulate the relative displacement history for each pair of nodes along the interface, and so for constant amplitude loading the load numerically applied to the structure (the cylinder model in this paper) was taken as constant and equal to the maximum value of the actual cyclic load. Consequently, the relative displacement calculated at the interface will be the envelope of its true cyclic variation with time.

In order to combine the relative displacement/stress relationship of the previous paragraph with a fatigue model, the rate of total damage (\dot{D}) is split into the sum of the static (\dot{D}_s) and fatigue (\dot{D}_f) components:

$$\dot{D} = \dot{D}_s + \dot{D}_f \quad (7)$$

If the stiffness degradation damage is adopted with the bilinear interface constitutive law, equation 5 is differentiated with respect to time in order to obtain the rate of static damage:

$$\frac{\partial D_s}{\partial t} = \dot{D}_s = \frac{\delta_0 \delta_c}{\delta_c - \delta_0} \frac{\dot{\delta}}{\delta^2} \quad \delta_0 < \delta < \delta_c \quad (8)$$

A cycle based formulation can be obtained from equation 8 by integrating over a number of loading cycles (ΔN) which yields

$$D_s(N + \Delta N) - D_s(N) = \frac{\delta_0 \delta_c}{\delta_c - \delta_0} \left(\frac{1}{\delta(N)} - \frac{1}{\delta(N + \Delta N)} \right) \quad (9)$$

where $\delta(N)$ is the current value of the amplitude of the displacement at N cycles and $\delta(N + \Delta N)$ is the value at $N + \Delta N$ cycles. Note that $\delta(N + \Delta N) \geq \delta(N)$ since the amplitude of the applied displacement is considered to be monotonically increasing. In a similar way $D_s(N)$ and $D_s(N + \Delta N)$ are the values of the static damage after N or $N + \Delta N$ cycles respectively. Equation 9 could have been obtained in a simpler way by expressing $D_s(N + \Delta N)$ and $D_s(N)$ with equation 5 and by computing the difference of the two

expressions. The procedure adopted here highlights the dependence of the static damage on the number of cycles rather than simply on the displacement amplitude.

If the stiffness degradation damage is adopted with the polynomial interface constitutive law, equation 6 can be used to derive an expression for the damage increment due to an increment of the number of loading cycles (ΔN)

$$D_s(N + \Delta N) - D_s(N) = \frac{\delta(N + \Delta N) - \delta(N)}{\delta_c} \left(2 - \frac{\delta(N + \Delta N) + \delta(N)}{\delta_c} \right) \quad (10)$$

In reference [12] the expression for the fatigue damage rate was proposed to have the following form:

$$\dot{D}_f = \frac{\partial D_f}{\partial t} = C e^{\lambda D} \left(\frac{\delta}{\delta_a} \right)^\beta \quad (11)$$

where C , λ and β are parameters which can be evaluated by comparison with interlaminar fatigue data and δ_a is a displacement-like quantity introduced for dimensional reasons. This was based on a formulation proposed in reference [12] for fatigue damage of continua. Following reference [6] it is possible to derive an expression for the increment of fatigue damage over a number of cycles ΔN :

$$D_f(N + \Delta N) - D_f(N) = \Delta N \frac{C}{1 + \beta} e^{\lambda D_\mu} \left(\frac{\delta_\mu}{\delta_c} \right)^{1+\beta} \quad (12)$$

where δ_a has been chosen equal to the failure displacement δ_c , and D_μ and δ_μ are defined according to reference [6] as:

$$\begin{aligned} D_\mu &= (1 - \mu)D(N) + \mu D(N + \Delta N) \\ \delta_\mu &= (1 - \mu)\delta(N) + \mu\delta(N + \Delta N) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

and μ assumes the value of 0.7.

Therefore by combining equations 7, 9 (for the case of bilinear constitutive law and stiffness degradation damage) and 12 the increment of total damage due to an increment ΔN of the number of cycles is given by the following expression:

$$D(N + \Delta N) - D(N) = \underbrace{\frac{\delta_0 \delta_c}{\delta_c - \delta_0} \left(\frac{1}{\delta(N)} - \frac{1}{\delta(N + \Delta N)} \right)}_{static} + \underbrace{\Delta N \frac{C}{1 + \beta} e^{\lambda D_\mu} \left(\frac{\delta_\mu}{\delta_c} \right)^{1+\beta}}_{fatigue} \quad (14)$$

Equation 14 defines implicitly the value of D after $N+\Delta N$ cycles since D appears on both sides of the equation. The damage value can be found by solving iteratively equation 14. In a similar way by combining equations 7, 10 (for the case of third order polynomial constitutive law and stiffness degradation damage) and 12 the increment of total damage due to an increment ΔN of the number of cycles is given by the following expression:

$$D(N + \Delta N) - D(N) = \underbrace{\frac{\delta(N + \Delta N) - \delta(N)}{\delta_c} \left(2 - \frac{\delta(N + \Delta N) + \delta(N)}{\delta_c} \right)}_{static} + \underbrace{\Delta N \frac{C}{1 + \beta} e^{\lambda D_\mu} \left(\frac{\delta_\mu}{\delta_c} \right)^{1+\beta}}_{fatigue} \quad (15)$$

COMPARISON OF THE TWO CONSTITUTIVE LAWS

The aim of the present section is to show how the cylinder model can be used to assess the performance of interface elements with the different constitutive laws previously introduced. Two important discretisation parameters, Δl and ΔN , are varied in order to investigate the sensitivity of the model. The best performing formulation will be the one which will allow the largest values for Δl and ΔN with the smallest variation in the slope of the curve x_{con} vs N .

Table 1: parameter values of the fatigue law to be adopted with the different constitutive laws or damage definitions in order to obtain similar Paris plots.

	C	β	λ	μ
Bilinear law, stiffness-degradation damage	2×10^{-6}	2.0	0.5	0.7
Polynomial law, stiffness-degradation damage	2.94×10^{-1}	5.5	0.5	0.7

Having fixed the fatigue law parameters as shown in table 1 in order to provide the same Paris plot for the two investigated formulations, the value of the applied moment was chosen to be $M_a = 0.2 M_c$ and the ‘exact slope’ (dx_{con}/dN) computed using a small value of Δl ($=0.005\text{mm}$) and ΔN ($=100$). (Any further reductions in these parameters produced negligible change in dx_{con}/dN *i.e.* the value of dx_{con}/dN can be considered as converged). M_c is the value of the quasi-static monotonically applied moment required to delaminate the two zero-thickness layers given by $M_c = G_c R$ and G_c is the critical energy release rate. The value of the ‘exact slope’ is approximately the same for the two formulations of table 1 since the values of C , β and λ were chosen to achieve this. After a few preliminary simulations it was decided to investigate the behaviour of the different formulations in the parameter field defined by the following ranges: $0.005\text{mm} \leq \Delta l \leq 0.30\text{mm}$; $100 < \Delta N < 75000$. The range of Δl values has been divided in 118 uniform subintervals and the range of ΔN values in 375 uniform subintervals so that 44250 different parameter combinations have been considered for each case.

Figure 3 shows a comparison between the performance of the bilinear constitutive law and that of the polynomial constitutive law, both with the stiffness degradation static damage definition. Different colours represent different errors in the computed slope

Figure 3: comparison of the error plots of the (a) bilinear constitutive law and of the (b) polynomial constitutive law.

with respect to that of the ‘exact solution’. For every formulation the error is computed with respect to the ‘exact slope’ of that formulation.

There are some interesting features that can be observed in Figure 3. The first feature is the formation of vertical bands with increasing ΔN at low values of Δl . These bands go from low error in the slope (dx_{con}/dN) on the left to higher errors on the right, where the slope computed is significantly greater than the ‘exact solution’. These bands simply indicate that for small Δl the error grows linearly with ΔN .

A second feature that can be observed is the pattern of many radial lines that seem to converge to the origin of the plot. These lines are made of ‘better’ results that are embedded in zones of ‘worse’ ones. These lines generate zones of ‘good’ results surrounded by ‘bad’ results. Further analysis was done of these radial features [11]. The main conclusion was that the ‘good’ results surrounded by ‘bad’ results do not correspond to reliable behaviour of the springs. They simply represent zones of bad parameter values in which different sources of error cancel each other out to provide a good result.

From figure 3 it is clear that the third order polynomial constitutive law is more sensitive than the bilinear constitutive law to changes in Δl and ΔN . The vertical bands of figure 3(b) are narrower than those of figure 3(a), which means that for a given value of Δl the error associated to a value of ΔN is usually bigger for the polynomial constitutive law than for the bilinear constitutive law. In general the small-error parameter combinations in figure 3(b) cover a smaller area than in figure 3(a). It can be concluded that the bilinear constitutive law is ‘better’ than the polynomial law.

CONCLUSIONS

A simple cylinder model has been introduced to compare in a systematic manner the behaviour of interface elements used to simulate fatigue crack propagation in composite materials.

Two constitutive laws (bilinear and third order polynomial) have been considered. One fatigue degradation strategy has been coupled to the two formulations and these have been implemented in the simple model to demonstrate its effectiveness.

The results show that the cylinder model can be used to readily assess the effectiveness of fatigue-driven delamination growth strategies. For the two formulations considered, the results of the model suggest that the bilinear constitutive model with the stiffness degradation damage formulation provides a better performance. The simple cylinder model is currently being used to explore the effectiveness of other fatigue-driven delamination growth strategies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

CLA acknowledges the financial support of the Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología, Mexico.

References

1. J.C.J. Schellekens and R. De Borst. A non-linear finite element approach for the analysis of mode I free edge delamination in composites. *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, **30**(9): 1239-1253, 1993.

2. N. Point and E. Sacco. A delamination model for laminated composites. *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, **33**(4): 483-509, 1996.
3. O. Allix and A. Corigliano. Modeling and simulation of crack propagation in mixed modes interlaminar fracture specimens. *Int. J. Fract.*, **77**: 111-140, 1996.
4. D.S. Dugdale. Yielding of steel sheets containing slits. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*; **8**:100 –104, 1960.
5. G. I. Barenblatt. The mathematical theory of equilibrium cracks in brittle fracture. *Advances in Applied Mechanics*, **7**:55-129, 1962.
6. P. Robinson, U. Galvanetto, D. Tumino, G. Bellucci, and D. Violeau. Numerical simulation of fatigue-driven delamination using interface elements. *International journal for numerical methods in engineering*, **63**(13):1824-1848, 2005.
7. J. J. Munoz, U. Galvanetto, and P. Robinson. On the numerical simulation of fatigue driven delamination with interface elements. *International journal of fatigue*, **28**(10):1136-1146, 2006.
8. J.C.J. Schellekens and R. De Borst. On the numerical integration of interface elements. *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, **36**: 43-66, 1993.
9. L. M. Kachanov. *Introduction to continuum damage mechanics*. Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, Dordrecht, 1986.
10. J. Lemaitre and J. L. Chaboche. *Mechanics of solid materials*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1994.
11. C. Lopez Armas. *Evaluation of Constitutive Laws for the Computer Simulation of Fatigue-Driven Delamination in Composite Materials*, PhD Thesis, Dept. Aeronautics, Imperial College London, 2008.
12. R. H. J. Peerlings, W. A. M. Brekelmans, R. de Borst, and M. G. D. Geers. Gradient-enhanced damage modelling of high-cycle fatigue. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, **49**(12): 1547 -1569, 2000.